

Relative elongation of deepwater rices

U. S. Singh and R. A. Pandey, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Chagharaghat, Bahraich 271901, Uttar Pradesh, India

Relative elongation of 14 deepwater rices at 1 and 2 months of submergence was studied in 3 replications at ARS, Chagharaghat, during 1981 kharif. Five seeds were sown in clay pots filled with 4 kg of a 3:1 mixture of airdried soil and farmyard manure. After 1 month seedlings were thinned to 1/pot. Three grams of urea were applied preplanting and 3 g diammonium phosphate were applied at 50 days when pots were transferred to deep water.

Height of the main culm to the highest auricle was recorded at 50 days. Plants were submerged in 50 cm water. Water level was raised 37 mm/day during the first month and 6 mm/day during the second month.

Before submergence Jalmagna check, Nang Dumto, RP31-49-2/LMN920356, Boon Nakh, Saran Kraham/RP31-49-2/LMN920349, and RP31-49-2/LMN920388

Relative elongation ability of deepwater rices, Ghagharaghat, India

Variety	Height before (cm)	Elongation	
		1-mo submergence (cm)	2-mo submergence (cm)
Jalmagna (check)	31	97	139
RP31-49-2/LMN920312	23	99	130
RP31-49-2/LMN920312-1	23	101	136
RP31-49-2/LMN920316-1	26	96	132
RP31-49-2/LMN920316-2	26	96	138
RP31-49-2/LMN920349	28	103	135
RP31-49-2/LMN920350	23	104	137
RP31-49-2/LMN920351	25	102	138
RP31-49-2/LMN920354	25	93	130
RP31-49-2/LMN920356	31	95	145
RP31-49-2/LMN920388	28	97	131
Nang Dumto	34	111	154
Saran Kraham	29	108	149
Boon Nakh	30	117	160
C. D. at 5%	4.2	6.9	7.3

were of similar, superior height (see table). After one month Boon Nakh, Nang Dumto, Saran Kraham, and RP31-49-2/LMN920350 had elongation superior to that of Jalmagna. After 2 months Boon Nakh, Nang Dumto, and Saran Kraham remained superior.

All rices had adequate, but widely

varying, elongation ability. Strains with superior growth under normal conditions were not necessarily superior under submergence. Some varieties grew faster early in submergence, but growth rate slowed later, resulting in relatively poor total performance. Further studies of this type should be conducted. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Genetics of cold tolerance at rice reproductive stage

S. Acharya, senior research fellow, and K. D. Sharma, professor and head, Plant Breeding Department, H. P. Agricultural University, Palampur 176062, H. P., India

The genetics of cold tolerance in rice has not been adequately defined because of the complex nature of plant response to cold environments and lack of reliable methods for scoring such response.

Two sets of 21 treatments of a 6-parent diallel using IR3941-45-Plp 2B,

IR579, Himdhan, IR2637-44-2, Zenith, and IR30, and their 15 F₁s, excluding reciprocals, were grown in a randomized block design with S replications. Fifteen-day-old seedlings, raised on sand in petri dishes, were transplanted in earthen pots filled with 2 parts soil, 1 part farmyard

Estimated general combining ability effects for cold tolerance, as measured through different character indices.^a

Parent	Days to flower	Effective tillers/hill	Yield/hill	Panicle weight	Panicle length	Spikelet fertility	Panicle exertion	Pollen fertility	Crude protein	Amylose	Gelatinization temperature
IR3941-45-Plp 2B	-0.74**	-0.61	-0.83**	-5.85**	0.47**	-11.50**	-11.46**	-2.47**	-2.26**	-0.11	-0.24
IR579	1.82**	-0.93**	2.79**	11.07**	0.99**	14.86**	12.46**	4.31**	3.58**	0.54*	-0.10
Himdhan	-0.77**	-0.73**	-2.21**	-1.85**	-1.63**	-4.15**	-5.66**	-1.16**	-1.02*	-3.70**	-3.34**
IR2637-44-2	-1.41**	2.86**	-3.30**	-7.56**	-0.51**	-7.22**	-28.74**	-2.07**	2.65**	1.16**	0.33
Zenith	2.08**	0.38	5.30**	9.08**	0.73**	13.50**	38.31**	3.48**	1.20**	3.86**	2.69**
IR30	-0.98**	-0.97**	-1.75**	-4.98**	-0.05	-5.49**	-4.91**	-2.09**	-4.15**	-1.75**	0.66**
SE _{(gi)±}	0.07	0.32	0.20	0.70	0.12	0.59	1.23	0.13	0.45	0.26	0.17
SE _{(gi-gi)±}	0.11	0.49	0.27	1.09	0.19	0.91	1.90	0.20	0.69	0.40	0.25

^a*Significant at $P = 0.05$, **significant at $P = 0.01$.